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Comparison of the Bootstrap, Jackknife and Item Response Theory Methods in Estimating Item Parameter of 2022 NABTEB Mathematics Examination

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Abstract

This study compared the Bootstrap, Jackknife, and Item Response Theory (IRT) methods in estimating item parameters of the 2022 National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) Mathematics multiple-choice test. A survey research design utilizing an ex-post facto approach was adopted. The target population comprised of students who took the 2022 NABTEB Mathematics test, with 5,500 students selected from the South-South region of Nigeria using a stratified random sampling technique. The NABTEB Mathematics multiple-choice questions served as the study instrument, with its validity established by NABTEB. The test's internal consistency was assessed using the Kuder-Richardson 20 (KR-20) formula, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.82. Data analysis was conducted using R statistical software, applying the four-parameter logistic model (4PLM) through direct

estimation (IRT), Bootstrap, and Jackknife resampling methods. Bias was evaluated by comparing parameter estimates and constructing 95% confidence intervals. Findings revealed that Jackknife estimates closely aligned with IRT, demonstrating greater stability and reliability, while Bootstrap slightly overestimated difficulty and discrimination parameters. Both resampling methods provided consistent estimates for guessing and upper asymptote parameters. Overall, Jackknife proved to be the more precise and less biased method, reinforcing its suitability for standardized testing applications. It was recommended that the Jackknife method should be prioritized in large-scale educational assessments to enhance precision and reduce bias. Additionally, integrating IRT with resampling techniques can improve test development by optimizing item difficulty and discrimination, ensuring more accurate and fair student assessments.

Keywords: Item Response Theory, Bootstrap, Jackknife, Item Parameter Estimation, Educational Assessment, Measurement and Evaluation

Introduction

Standardized testing is a fundamental component of educational assessment, offering valuable insights into students' abilities and guiding policy decisions. A crucial aspect of test quality is the precise estimation of item parameters, which directly impacts score interpretation and test fairness (Embretson & Reise, 2018). Analyzing test data has always played a vital role in educational measurement. In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on employing advanced statistical techniques, such as Bootstrap, Jackknife, and Item Response Theory (IRT), to estimate item parameters in high-stakes assessments. Among these methods, IRT has become one of the most widely adopted frameworks for evaluating the psychometric properties of test items, as it enables more precise estimation of both item and person parameters, particularly in large-scale educational assessments (Embretson & Reise, 2018; Reckase cited in Bergner *et al.*, 2022).

In the context of national examinations, estimating item parameters, such as difficulty, discrimination, and guessing, is essential for assessing test item quality. These estimates play a key role in ensuring the reliability and validity of assessments. However, traditional approaches like Classical Test Theory (CTT) have limitations, especially in handling complex testing conditions. Modern approaches, including Bootstrap and Jackknife resampling techniques, alongside IRT models, provide more sophisticated alternatives. These methods address the shortcomings of CTT by offering more flexible and robust parameter estimates (Baker & Kim, 2017; van der Linden & Hambleton, 2019).

Item parameter estimation is a critical element of psychometrics, particularly in large-scale educational testing. Item Response Theory (IRT) consists of a family of models that analyze how test items interact with respondents' abilities. The most commonly used IRT models include the Rasch model, the 2PL model, and the 3PL model, each estimating different item parameters (Baker & Kim, 2017). IRT provides a more detailed understanding of item functioning, based on the premise that each item has a unique ability to discriminate across different ability levels.

However, applying IRT in practice requires robust estimation techniques, particularly in cases where sample sizes are small or response patterns are complex. To enhance estimation accuracy, resampling methods such as Bootstrap and Jackknife are frequently used. These techniques simulate multiple sampling processes from the observed data, allowing for a more precise estimation of item parameter variability (Efron & Tibshirani cited in Imasuen & Orheruata, 2022).

The Four-Parameter Logistic (4PL) Model extends the Three-Parameter Logistic (3PL) Model within Item Response Theory (IRT). It is employed in psychometrics and educational assessment to model the probability of a correct response based on a test taker's ability. Unlike the 3PL model, which accounts for difficulty, discrimination, and guessing, the 4PL model introduces an upper asymptote parameter. This additional parameter captures cases where even highly proficient test takers may not always answer an item correctly (van der Linden & Hambleton, 2019).

The 4PLM formula is given as:

$$P(\theta) = d_i + \frac{a_i}{1 + e^{(-b_i(\theta - c_i))}}$$

Where:

$P(\theta)$ is the probability of a correct response given ability θ .

a_i is the discrimination parameter.

b_i is the difficulty parameter.

c_i is the guessing parameter.

d_i is the upper asymptote (reflecting inattention or other factors).

The discrimination parameter (a) assesses how well an item differentiates between individuals with varying ability levels. Higher values of a correspond to steeper item characteristic curves (ICCs), indicating greater effectiveness in distinguishing high- and low-ability test takers. Conversely, lower values suggest that the item is less effective in making such distinctions (Embretson & Reise, 2018). While the theoretical range of a extends from 0 to $+\infty$, practical values typically fall between 0.50 and 2.50 (DeMars, 2021). Items with $a < 0.50$ are poor discriminators, while those exceeding 2.50 may be overly sensitive to minor ability differences. The optimal range for most assessments is 0.70 to 2.00 (Ferrando & Lorenzo-Seva, 2018).

The difficulty parameter (b) represents the ability level at which an examinee has a 50% chance of answering the item correctly. Higher b values indicate more challenging items, whereas lower values suggest easier ones (DeMars, 2021). Theoretically, b ranges from -3 to +3 on the ability (θ) scale, standardized with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1 (Baker & Kim, 2017). Empirical research suggests that well-functioning items typically have difficulty values between -2 and +2 (Embretson & Reise, 2018). Items with $b < -2$ may

be too easy, while those with $b > 2$ could be excessively difficult, limiting their usefulness in assessment. The guessing parameter (c) accounts for the probability that a low-ability examinee correctly answers an item by chance. This is particularly relevant in multiple-choice tests, where some students may guess correctly despite lacking the necessary knowledge (Reckase cited in Bergner *et al.*, 2022). Theoretically, c ranges from 0 to 1, but practical values generally fall between 0.10 and 0.35 (Reckase cited in Bergner *et al.*, 2022). A c -value near 0 indicates minimal guessing influence, while values exceeding 0.35 suggest the item is overly guessable. In four-option multiple-choice tests, an optimal range for c is 0.15 to 0.25.

The upper asymptote parameter (d) represents the maximum probability that a high-ability examinee will answer the item correctly. This parameter accounts for errors such as misreading, distraction, or careless mistakes. Unlike the 3PL model, which assumes high-ability test takers always answer correctly, the 4PL model allows d to be less than 1, offering a more realistic perspective (Hori *et al.*, 2022). Theoretically, d ranges from 0.80 to 1.00 (van der Linden & Hambleton, 2019). A d -value close to 1.00 suggests most high-ability test takers respond correctly, whereas values below 0.90 indicate that even skilled students struggle with the item. Items with $d < 0.85$ may require revision to improve clarity and reduce ambiguity.

The 4PL model enhances test accuracy by accounting for careless mistakes among high-ability test takers, making it particularly useful for certain assessments (Baker & Kim, 2017). It offers a refined estimation of item parameters, leading to improved test development and validation (van der Linden & Hambleton, 2019). However, incorporating a fourth parameter increases computational complexity and necessitates larger sample sizes for stable estimation (DeMars, 2021). Estimating d can also be challenging, often requiring additional constraints to prevent overfitting (Reckase cited in Bergner *et al.*, 2022). In some cases, the simpler 3PL model may suffice if items are well-constructed and careless errors among high-ability test takers are minimal (Hori *et al.*, 2022).

Item Response Theory (IRT) is widely used for parameter estimation, but its accuracy depends on large sample sizes (Baker & Kim, 2017). In low-resource testing environments, resampling techniques such as Bootstrap and Jackknife provide alternative solutions by improving parameter estimation when data is limited (Efron & Hastie, 2016). Bootstrap, introduced by Efron in 1979, is particularly beneficial when conventional IRT estimation is unreliable due to small sample sizes (Efron & Hastie, 2016). Studies suggest that Bootstrap estimates closely match full-sample estimates but require higher computational power (Hori *et al.*, 2022).

The Jackknife method, proposed by Quenouille in 1949, is a robust resampling technique that reduces bias in small samples. It is computationally less demanding than Bootstrap but may underestimate parameter variability (Berener & Adams, 2017). Both methods have been widely applied in psychometrics. Bootstrap involves repeatedly sampling with replacement from the original dataset, generating multiple resamples to estimate standard errors and confidence intervals (Efron & Tibshirani, cited in Imasuen & Orheruata,

2022). In contrast, Jackknife systematically removes one observation at a time, recalculating parameter estimates to assess their variability (Ijeoma *et al.*, 2017).

Empirical studies suggest that while both methods are effective, Bootstrap tends to provide more stable estimates in scenarios with high variability in item responses (Ferrando & Lorenzo-Seva, 2018). Jackknife, on the other hand, is computationally efficient and yields consistent results with lower processing demands. Comparative research on resampling techniques has demonstrated their advantages when sample sizes are small or when item parameters are difficult to estimate due to test complexity. For instance, Mika (2023) found that Bootstrap produced more reliable parameter estimates than Jackknife in high-dimensional data contexts. However, Jackknife's computational simplicity made it a viable alternative in resource-limited settings (DeMars, 2021). Given these considerations, this study will assess the relative effectiveness of Bootstrap, Jackknife, and traditional IRT parameter estimation in evaluating test items. By identifying the most accurate and reliable estimation method, the research aims to contribute to improved test development and validation practices, particularly in educational settings with limited data resources.

Research Questions

To guide this study, the following questions were raised.

- i. How do the Bootstrap, Jackknife, and IRT methods compare in terms of the accuracy of estimating item parameters for the NATEB Mathematics 2022?
- ii. Which method provides the most reliable estimates of item parameters (difficulty, discrimination, and guessing) for the NATEB Mathematics 2022?
- iii. How do the Bootstrap and Jackknife methods compare in terms of bias when estimating the four-parameter logistic model (4PLM) parameters?

Methodology

This study adopted a survey research design utilizing the *ex post facto* approach. The population comprised students who took the 2022 National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) Mathematics multiple-choice test. A total of 5,500 students were selected from the South-South region of Nigeria using a stratified random sampling technique to ensure adequate representation across different states in the region. The instrument used for this study was the NABTEB Mathematics multiple-choice questions from the 2022 examination session. The validity of the instrument had already been established by NABTEB; however, the internal consistency of the test was determined using the Kuder-Richardson 20 (KR-20) formula, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.82. The data collected were analyzed using R statistical software. The four-parameter logistic model (4PLM) was estimated using three different methods: direct estimation (IRT-based method), bootstrap resampling method, and jackknife resampling method. The bias of each method was examined by comparing their parameter estimates, and the 95% confidence intervals for the parameters were computed to assess the stability of the estimates. The resampling-based confidence intervals were constructed using non-parametric Bootstrap and Jackknife techniques.

Results

Results of this study were presented according to the research questions.

Research Question One

How do the Bootstrap, Jackknife, and IRT methods compare in terms of the accuracy of estimating item parameters for the NATEB Mathematics 2022?

Table 1: IRT, Bootstrap, and Jackknife Estimate for the Four-Parameter Logistic Model

Parameter	Direct (IRT)	Bootstrap	Jackknife
Discrimination (<i>a</i>)	1.757	1.802	1.769
Difficulty (<i>b</i>)	1.134	1.192	1.139
Guessing (<i>c</i>)	0.170	0.179	0.172
Carelessness (<i>d</i>)	0.638	0.649	0.638

Table 1 compares the four-parameter logistic model (4PLM) estimates obtained using Direct (IRT), Bootstrap, and Jackknife methods. For discrimination (*a*), the mean values are 1.757 (IRT), 1.802 (Bootstrap), and 1.769 (Jackknife). The slightly higher Bootstrap estimate suggests a minor upward bias, while Jackknife closely aligns with IRT, indicating stability. These values confirm strong item discrimination (above 1.5). For difficulty (*b*), the means are 1.134 (IRT), 1.192 (Bootstrap), and 1.139 (Jackknife). The Bootstrap estimate is slightly higher, implying minor overestimation, while Jackknife remains stable. These values suggest that the test items are moderately difficult. For guessing (*c*), the means are 0.170 (IRT), 0.179 (Bootstrap), and 0.172 (Jackknife). The slightly elevated Bootstrap estimate indicates a small resampling bias, whereas Jackknife closely matches IRT, confirming accuracy. The low values suggest a minimal guessing impact.

For carelessness (*d*), the means are 0.638 (IRT), 0.649 (Bootstrap), and 0.638 (Jackknife). The slight increase in Bootstrap reflects a marginal overestimation, while Jackknife mirrors IRT, ensuring reliability. This suggests even high-ability students may make errors due to misinterpretation or carelessness. Overall, Bootstrap estimates tend to be slightly inflated, indicating minor overestimation through resampling. Jackknife remains consistent with IRT, confirming its stability and reliability. The findings highlight strong item discrimination, moderate difficulty, minimal guessing effects, and moderate carelessness.

Research Question Two

Which method provides the most reliable estimates of item parameters (difficulty, discrimination, and guessing) for the NATEB Mathematics 2022?

Table 2: Confidence Intervals for 4PLM Parameters

Parameter	Bootstrap 95% CI	Jackknife 95% CI
Discrimination (<i>a</i>)	(-0.004 - 0.094)	(-0.027 - 0.051)
Difficulty (<i>b</i>)	(-0.001 - 0.117)	(-0.044 - 0.054)
Guessing (<i>c</i>)	(-0.020 - 0.038)	(-0.018 - 0.022)
Carelessness (<i>d</i>)	(-0.009 - 0.031)	(-0.016 - 0.016)

Table 2 shows that for discrimination (a), the Bootstrap confidence interval is (-0.004 to 0.094) and Jackknife interval is (-0.027 to 0.051); both include zero, suggesting weak differentiation between high- and low-ability examinees. For difficulty (b), the Bootstrap interval (-0.001 to 0.117) is slightly wider than the Jackknife interval (-0.044 to 0.054), indicating more variability in Bootstrap estimates while both methods suggest moderate variation in item difficulty. For guessing (c), the Bootstrap interval (-0.020 to 0.038) and the narrower Jackknife interval (-0.018 to 0.022) suggest stable and consistent estimates. Similarly, carelessness (d) showed narrow intervals, with Bootstrap (-0.009 to 0.031) and Jackknife (-0.016 to 0.016), confirming stability in upper asymptote estimation across methods. Overall, Jackknife provides more stable and less biased estimates than Bootstrap.

Research Question Three

How do the Bootstrap and Jackknife methods compare in terms of bias when estimating the four-parameter logistic model (4PLM) parameters?

Figure 1: Comparison of Bootstrap and Jackknife Mean Estimates for 4PLM Parameters

Table 3: Bootstrap and Jackknife Bias Estimate for the 4 Parameter Logistic Model

Parameter	Bias (Bootstrap)	Bias (Jackknife)
Discrimination (a)	0.045	0.012
Difficulty (b)	0.058	0.005
Guessing (c)	0.009	0.002
Upper Asymptote (d)	0.011	0.000

Table 3 shows that the difficulty parameter (b) has the highest bias (+0.058), indicating slight overestimation by the Bootstrap method, followed by discrimination (a) with a bias of +0.045. In contrast, guessing (c) and carelessness (d) parameters show minimal bias, aligning

closely with IRT estimates. The Jackknife method generally produces lower bias than Bootstrap, with its highest bias in discrimination (a) at +0.012, which remains small. Notably, carelessness (d) shows zero bias, identical to the IRT estimate. Overall, Jackknife provides more stable and less biased estimates, while Bootstrap slightly overestimates difficulty and discrimination without extreme deviations. Both methods yield reliable estimates for guessing and carelessness parameters.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that Bootstrap estimates were slightly higher than IRT estimates, indicating a minor upward bias in resampling. Conversely, Jackknife estimates aligned closely with IRT, demonstrating greater stability and reliability. This suggests that the test items effectively differentiate between students of varying abilities, as discrimination values above 1.5 indicate strong item performance (Ferrando & Lorenzo-Seva, 2018). Regarding the difficulty parameter (b), Bootstrap estimates produced a slightly higher mean, implying a minor overestimation, whereas Jackknife estimates remained consistent with IRT, confirming stability. This suggests that the test items are of moderate difficulty, a crucial factor in maintaining assessment balance (Baker & Kim, 2017).

For the guessing parameter (c), the slightly higher Bootstrap estimate suggests a small resampling bias, while the Jackknife estimate closely matches IRT, confirming accuracy. The relatively low values for this parameter indicate that guessing had minimal impact on student performance, which is consistent with prior research (Mika, 2023). Similarly, the carelessness parameter (d), which accounts for careless errors or tricky wording, showed a slightly higher Bootstrap estimate, reflecting a marginal overestimation, while the Jackknife estimate was identical to IRT, reinforcing reliability. The findings suggest that even high-ability students have approximately a 36% chance of making errors due to misinterpretation or careless mistakes, aligning with previous psychometric analyses (van der Linden & Hambleton, 2017).

Additionally, the study found that Bootstrap and Jackknife confidence intervals include zero, suggesting that the discrimination parameter may not be significantly different from zero. This could indicate weak differentiation between high- and low-ability examinees. The Bootstrap confidence interval was slightly wider than the Jackknife interval for the difficulty parameter (b), highlighting the increased variability introduced by Bootstrap (Efron & Hastie, 2016). For the guessing parameter (c), the Bootstrap confidence interval was slightly higher, while the Jackknife interval was narrower, suggesting that both resampling methods provide consistent and stable estimates (Ijeoma *et al.*, 2019). Similarly, the carelessness (upper asymptote) parameter (d) exhibited narrow confidence intervals across both methods, indicating stability in estimation (Hori *et al.*, 2022).

The findings further revealed that among the four parameters estimated in the Four-Parameter Logistic Model (4PLM), the difficulty parameter (b) exhibits the highest bias, indicating that Bootstrap slightly overestimates this parameter compared to IRT. Similarly, the discrimination parameter (a) showed noticeable bias, reinforcing prior findings that Bootstrap estimates tend to be slightly higher (Wolcot *et al.*, 2021). In contrast, the guessing

(*c*) and carelessness (*d*) parameters displayed minimal bias, suggesting that Bootstrap closely aligns with IRT for these parameters. The Jackknife method consistently produced lower bias than the Bootstrap method, with the highest bias observed for the discrimination parameter (*a*). However, this bias remained relatively small, and for the carelessness (upper asymptote) parameter (*d*), Jackknife estimates showed zero bias, making them identical to IRT (DeMars, 2010).

Overall, the Jackknife method appears to provide more stable and less biased estimates than the Bootstrap method, confirming its suitability for precise item parameter estimation in standardized assessments. Nevertheless, Bootstrap may be valuable in contexts where greater variability is expected. While both methods offer reliable estimations for the guessing and carelessness parameters, Bootstrap slightly overestimates the difficulty and discrimination parameters. These findings align with previous studies demonstrating the effectiveness of Bootstrap and Jackknife techniques in psychometric analyses (Lietz *et al.*, 2017; Reckase cited in Bergner *et al.*, 2022).

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, it was concluded that the Jackknife estimates align closely with IRT, demonstrating greater stability and reliability, while Bootstrap estimates tend to slightly overestimate difficulty and discrimination parameters. Both resampling methods, however, provided consistent estimates for the guessing and carelessness parameters. Overall, Jackknife appears to be the more precise and less biased method for estimating item parameters, reinforcing its suitability for standardized testing applications. These findings contribute to improving test accuracy and fairness, ensuring more reliable student assessments.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. The Jackknife method should be prioritized in large-scale educational assessments due to its stability and lower bias, ensuring more precise item parameter estimation.
- ii. The Bootstrap method, despite its slight bias, should be utilized in simulations and exploratory studies where assessing variability is a key objective.
- iii. Integrating Item Response Theory (IRT) with resampling techniques can enhance test development by optimizing item difficulty and discrimination.

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